

Event metadata

Event title	MaveDB: discovery and interpretation of high-throughput functional assay data
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	26/03/2024
Time of event	1pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>Multiplexed assays of variant effect (MAVEs) are a family of experimental techniques that measure all single amino acid or single nucleotide changes in a gene or other functional element. MaveDB is an international community database that enables discovery and reuse of data from these experiments. It provides a platform for integrating large-scale measurements of sequence variant impact with applications that can be used to interpret the data for basic and clinical research.</p> <p>In this webinar we consider:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are MAVEs and how are the experiments performed? • How much MAVE data is available in MaveDB and how is it organised? • Who can submit datasets to MaveDB? • What are some of the clinical applications for MAVEs and how is the data being used to understand patient variants?
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/mavedb
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Genetic variation Functional annotation
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au

Audience	Anyone with an interest in high-throughput functional assays for research or clinical applications.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of this webinar you should be able to outline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What MAVEs are and how are the experiments performed. • How much MAVE data is available in MaveDB and how is it organised. • Who can submit datasets to MaveDB • Some of the clinical applications for MAVEs and how is the data being used to understand patient variants
Speakers	Dr Alan Rubin, Senior Research Officer, WEHI
Related material	None